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NEUROPLASTICITY & EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE - ALLIED TO THE COMMANDERS OF THE MILITARY FIRE DEPARTMENT / SOUTHERN REGION - GOIÁS

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ABSTRACT

This study, through the capacity of cerebral neuroplasticity, allows us to increase the level of emotional intelligence in the actions of Military Fire Brigade commanders in their troops.